

Analysis of Quizizz Implementation on the Learning Interest of Students in Class XIF5 at Senior High School 3 Surakarta

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Abstract:

Quizizz is an alternative e-learning-based evaluation tool that can be used by students and provides quick results for teachers to make decisions about remedial or enrichment actions. Quizizz is an online quiz learning medium that can be easily accessed via a browser or downloaded through a playstore. Quizizz is an implementation of the use of computer technology in learning. The student's learning interest should be developed with distance learning as a means for the student to perform tasks and discussions without having to do face-to-face learning. The aim of the research is to find out the impact of Quizizz implementation use on the learning interest of students in XIF5 class on computer network and Internet material at Senior High School 3 Surakarta. Research uses descriptive qualitative research methods. The subjects of the study were one computer science teacher and 10 students in the XIF5 class who were selected by systematic random sampling. Data collection techniques are using interviews and questionnaires as well as analyzing data with data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawings. The results of the research can be concluded that the use of Quizizz was able to increase the interest of students of XIF5 class in the study of Computer Network and Internet materials at Senior High School 3 Surakarta.

Keywords: *Computer networks and the Internet, learning interests, quizizz.*

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Introduction

The Indonesian education world is considered to have not yet reached the point of success that is expected jointly. There are so many and so complicated problems that it's hard to find a way out of them. Education in Indonesia has been very worrying lately because of the decline in the quality of education due to some problems in the Indonesian education system. The number of weaknesses in the education management sector, the gaps in educational resources and facilities in urban and rural areas, the weak support of the government, the presence of an ancient mindset in society, the low quality of teaching resources, as well as poor standards of evaluation of learning (Fitri, 2021).

Modern times like these are many technologies that are rapidly evolving and are beginning to be exploited. This is demonstrated by the increasing number of information technology users from the top to the bottom. Informatics is an advancement in the field of information that makes it easier to perform tasks or routines to obtain information or disseminate information. (Karim et al., 2020). The advances in computer science provide benefits in terms of improved performance and increased efficiency in the field of education. Informatics can be used as a form of distance learning developed to facilitate students in viewing schedules, working and submitting tasks, seeing values, as well as conducting group discussions with unlimited space anywhere and at any time without having to do face-to-face learning.

Quizizz is a quiz-shaped learning medium that is done online. Quizizz is an interactive multimedia pattern that is easy to use as a learning medium as well as evaluation material (Salsabila et al., 2020). The Quizizz app has a variety of learning media such as quizzes, daily assessments, semester exam surveys and so on. Quizizz can be easily accessed through a browser or downloaded through the playstore. Quizizz has the advantage of preventing each other from interacting with each other because the questions given to the students one with the other are presented randomly. Quizizz is an alternative e-learning-based evaluation tool that can be used to evaluate students and provide quick results for teachers to make decisions about remedial or enrichment actions.

The previous study on Quizizz was conducted by Al Haddar and Juliano (2021), entitled "Analysis of Quizizz learning media in online learning in elementary school students" with the findings that Quizizz is able to increase the motivation and interest of learners. Another research was conducted by Mulyati and Evendi (2020), with the title "Mathematical learning through Quizizz game media to improve the learning outcomes of mathematics in secondary school" which aims to find out the improvement of learning outcome of pupils on the material of Pythagoras theorem class VIIA at SMPN 2 Bojonegara. The research carried out by Citra and Rosy (2020) on Quizizz with the title "Effectiveness of the use of learning media based on educational games Quizizz on learning technology outcomes of the office of students X grade SMK Ketintang Surabaya" discusses the effectiveness and use of Quizizz to improve the learning outcome of pupils. Therefore, the selection of Quizizz learning media can boost the enthusiasm of the student at the time of learning. Quizizz is a learning system that can enhance effective learning processes and can cultivate a positive sense of competition among students.

Based on observations carried out at Senior High School 3 Surakarta, researchers found problems in the interest of pupils in learning because the learning media used by teachers was less attractive. Many students often leave the classroom when teachers conduct assessments, and there is a conflict between students.

Based on this background, the researchers realized the importance of knowing the influence of Quizizz Implementation use on the learning interest of students of XIF5 class on Computer Network and Internet material at Senior High School 3 Surakarta. Research was conducted in order to obtain the Certificate of Educator as a Professional Teacher at the University of Eleven March Surakarta. Therefore, the researchers are interested in conducting a study entitled "Analysis of Quizizz Implementation on the Learning Interest of Students in Class XIF5 at Senior High School 3 Surakarta".

Related Work

Quizizz is one of the learning tools or media that is believed to be able to instill the interest of learners through its interesting features. Quizizz is an application designed to create interactive multiplayer quizzes that can be accessed from any device such as, computers, smartphones, and tablets. quizizz is a game-based learning application that brings multiplayer activity into the classroom and makes classroom training interactive and fun (Purba, 2019). While Quizizz can track the sequence of each student, Quizizz also can provide homework to be practiced by the student.

Before understanding in depth about the use of the application Quizizz as a learning medium, this application must have some advantages that can support the success of the learning process in high school students: 1) For Teachers/Teachers, it makes it easier to make questions. 2) When answering questions or quiz correctly, after that will appear how many points are obtained in one question, also get a ranking or rating in answering the quiz. 3) When the

student answers the quiz wrong, then appears the correct answer, for self-correction for the student. 4) When it has been stated completed the quiz, at the end or closing session, will be previously displayed review question to reflect Back the selected answer. 5) In the work of a quiz, each student gets different questions, because they have been checked automatically, thus minimizing fraud.

Interest in learning is a feeling of pleasure and interest in the learning process that arises from knowing the behavior of enthusiastic learners. Interests in learning can also be understood as a tendency to direct attention and interest to physical and spiritual activities that lead to human growth and development, including creativity, taste, mind, spirituality, knowledge, as well as mental and physical abilities. (Nasution, 2022).

Internal factors are some influence that originates from within the pupil: attention, attitudes, talents, and abilities of a pupil (Rolina and Efendi, 2023). External factors are influenced from outside, such as attention in the learning process, means and facilities of learning guidance of parents on learning at home facilities and needs made by parents as well as environmental factors that cause one of the factors affecting learning interests.

Indicators of interest in learning include: (1) the desire to know to have something, (2) the objects or activities that are, (3) the type of activity to obtain something that is, and (4) the efforts made to realize a desire. Pleasure in a particular object or activity. In relation to the student's learning interests, the indicator is a monitoring tool that can give clues to the interests of the student.

Computer networks and the Internet were important inventions of the 20th century that were capable of changing human lives. The Internet is formed from a global network of computers capable of connecting computer devices, laptops, and activities owned by an individual to a network or to other devices. The Internet involves billions of devices connected globally where one device can request services to another device. After studying this material, students are expected to be able to explain and design a simple network topology that can connect multiple computers, explain and utilize a computer network model, as well as to explain the mechanisms of transmission, reception, and communication of data.

Research Method

Research using a qualitative approach is an approach that exhibits in depth on the subject being studied both directly and indirectly. Qualitative research focuses on understanding social phenomena from a participant's perspective by focusing more on a complete picture rather than detailing it into interrelated variables. Qualitative research can not be measured using statistical procedures to produce results of research that are descriptive (Mappasere and Suyuti, 2019). The research is conducted using the type of research. Descriptive research is a form of research carried out with the method of collecting as many data as possible to give an overview of the impact of the use of learning media Quizizz implementation on the learning interest of students of class XIF5 on the materials of Computer Networks and the Internet at Senior High School 3 Surakarta.

The research is located at Senior High School 3 Surakarta with the object of research is a teacher of information technology subjects, pupils consisting of 36 pupils of XIF5 class are sampled into 10 pupils randomly using the technique of systematic random sampling. Research is done by collecting data, processing, and describing the results. The descriptions analyzed according to the conditions that occurred at the time of the research are real and objective. Researchers will observe and record about Quizizz as a tool for assessing learning outcomes in quizzes at Senior High School 3 Surakarta

Interviews are conducted by asking questions directly orally to the research object. The interview technique is used by researchers to obtain data and dig information from teachers and students of Senior High School 3 Surakarta in the planning and implementation of Quizizz as a tool for evaluating learning outcomes. The quizier technique is almost the same as the interview technique but it is done by providing structured questions as a basis and guidelines to take information about the influence of quizizz in improving the learning interest of students.

Data analysis is done using qualitative descriptive methods by describing all the results obtained during the research process. Data analysis process is done through the process of data reduction, presentation of data, as well as drawing conclusions. The data analysis is done using a valuation scale called the Likert Scale. The Likert scale is the valuation used to measure the opinion, attitude, or behavior of a person or a group of people. In the Likert scale, the variable to be measured is described as a variable indicator. After that, the indicator will be used as a pushpoint to compile various instruments. The response of any instrument using the Likert scale has a gradation from very positive to very negative or vice versa. The advantage of the Likert scale is that it is easy to apply, it is free to define questions or statements according to the context of the problem discussed in a study, the answer to an option can be an alternative so that information about the choice can be clarified, and the measurement results can be obtained quickly.

Result and Discussion

The study was conducted on Tuesday, April 2, 2024 in the XIF5 classroom of Senior High School 3 Surakarta. The interview was conducted with Mr. Jumari, S.T. with the following interview instruments:

Table 1. Results of Interviews with Teachers of Computer Networking and Internet Materials at Senior High School 3 Surakarta

No	Question	Answer
1	How to use Quizizz learning media?	With the use of Quizizz then learning becomes fun, able to expel boredom for pupils. Quizizz can also make pupils think creative
2	What is the influence of Quizizz on the Computer Network and Internet subjects?	The impact can improve motivation and competitiveness among healthy learners because the results of the work can appear in real time
3	Anyone using the Quizizz app?	Teachers and Students
4	Are you happy in using the Quizizz app at the time of learning?	For me, it's very fun, sister, because in the quizizz app there's a lot of fun features.
5	How do you use quizz on the learning process of computer networks and the Internet?	Because in can grow a good understanding for the delivery of material, can grow, enhance our knowledge well.

Based on the results of interviews with teachers, Quizizz learning media provides many benefits in computer networking and Internet subjects. The use of learning media Quizizz provides benefits such as improving the concentration of pupils, improving pupil learning outcomes, increasing pupil motivation, as well as providing effective and efficient learning. (Tusyani et al., 2022).

Based on the results of the questionnaire, there are 10 statements divided into 10 tables. Each of the statements is categorized into the answers Very agree, Agree, Disagree, and Very disagree. The respondents consisted of 10 students in the XIF5 class at the Senior High School 3 Surakarta.

Table 2. Use of learning media Quizizz makes it easier for students to understand the materials Computer Networking and Internet that have been taught

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
6	4	0	0

10 students were given a questionnaire stating that the use of Quizizz learning media made it easier for students to understand the Computer Network and Internet materials they had been taught. Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 6 people. The students who responded with an agreed total of 4 people. Students who replied with a disagreement total of 0 people. Participants who reputed with a different number of people. Answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each earned a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statement to get a score in a row are 24, 12, 0, and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz makes it easier for students to understand the materials Computer networks and the Internet that have been taught by teachers in the classroom during learning activities. According to Handayani et al., (2023) Quizizz is a learning medium that can be used to convey student learning material while also becoming an interesting and enjoyable learning evaluation medium.

Table 3. Use of learning media Quizizz increases the interest of students in learning materials Computer Networks and the Internet

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
7	3	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 7 people. The students who responded with an agreed number of 3 people. Students who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people. Student responding with a non-agreement amount of 0 persons. The answers were very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree with a maximum of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores were summed up so that for the first statement to get a score in a row were 28, 9, 0 and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz increased the student's interest in learning materials Computer networks and the Internet that were taught by teachers

in the classroom during learning activities. Muliani and Arusman (2022) revealed that an interest in learning generates interest in something or activity without compulsion. Interest in learning plays an important role for the student as it is the key to the active participation of the student in learning. According to Benufinit and Malaikosa (2024), the student's interest in learning will influence learning outcomes. The higher the interest of the student, the higher will be the student's learning outcome.

Table 4. Quizizz learning media can be used by teachers and pupils to facilitate learning activities in schools

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
8	2	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of eight people. The students who responded with an agreed number of two people. Students who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people. Student responding with a negative number of zero people. Answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each get a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statement gets a score in a row is 32, 6, 0 and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz can be used by teachers and students so that it facilitates learning activities in the school. According to Noviatami et al. (2024), learning media is a device or a tool that can be used to support the learning process as well as to be an intermediary between teachers and pupils to be able to channel information to each other. Quizizz is one of the forms of technology development that can help learning activities become more enjoyable.

Table 5. Learning media Quizizz can improve the skills and skills of pupils

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
6	4	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 6 people. The students who responded with an agreed number of 4 people. Students who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people. Student responding with a different number of people. Answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each got a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statements to get a score in a row are 24, 16, 0, and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the learning media Quizizz can improve the skills and skills of the participants. According to Muliani and Arusman (2022), learning is an activity process of acquiring knowledge of attitudes and skills. Learning is not just about a formal lesson but encompasses skills, skills, interests, and habits that influence the psychological interests of learners.

Table 6. Quizizz learning media can enhance a positive sense of competition among pupils.

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
8	2	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of eight people. The students who responded with an agreed number of two. The respondents who replied with a disagreement number of none. The participants who replied with no agreement numbered zero. The answers were very agreed, agree, disagree and disagreed very much each got a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores were summed up so that for the first statements to get a score in a row were 32, 6, 0, and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz can increase the sense of positive competition between the students. Noviatami et al., (2024) revealed that Quizizz is one of the platform applications that enables teachers to make interactive quizzes so that students can participate using their digital devices. Quizizz has interesting features such as the design of systems, competitive evaluation, and can increase enthusiasm of participants in learning activities.

Table 7. Quizizz learning media provides a new atmosphere for student learning activities

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
5	5	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 5 people. The students who responded with an agreed number of 5 persons. The respondents who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people.

the students that answered with no agreement amounted to 0 individuals. The answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each earned a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statement to get a score in a row are 20, 15, 0 and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the Computer Network and Internet material presented in the form of learning media Quizizz provides a new atmosphere for the learning activities of the students. According to Hidayati and Aslam (2021), Quizizz learning media is considered an attractive learning medium because it gives a new environment and makes it easier for students to understand the given material.

Table 8. Students become more motivated in learning because of the unique learning medium Quizizz

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
6	4	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 6 people. The students who responded with an agreed number of 4 people. Students who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people. Participants who replied with a different number of people. Answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each earned a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statement to get a score in a row are 24, 12, 0, and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of the learning media Quizizz makes the students more motivated in learning because of the unique learning medium Quizizz. Sulaiman (2022) revealed that motivation is the impulse within the student to a specific goal. Learning motivation can increase the learning spirit within the pupil. Learning Motivation contains an effort to reach a learning goal to understand the material and make development in learning. Low learning motivation will have a negative impact on the student so as to cause low success in learning and performance of the student. The motivation of learning between the student and the other pupil is different so that it can affect the learning process.

Table 9. Learning with Quizizz media improves the critical and creative thinking ability of the pupils

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
4	6	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 4 people. The students who responded with an agreed total of 6 people. Students who replied with a disagreement total of 0 people. Participants who replied with a different number of people. Answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each got a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statements to get a score in a row are 16, 18, 0 and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz can improve the students' ability to think critically and creatively. According to Samura (2019), critical thinking is a concept of reasoned and reflective thinking that emphasizes decision-making about what to believe and do. Critical thinking is a pattern of thinking that can be developed through both formal and non-formal educational processes. There is an intervention of an educator in the concept of critical thinking that is able to help the student understand, solve and conclude the problems they are thinking.

Table 10. Quizizz learning media is able to increase the confidence of the students in answering the various questions given.

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
5	5	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 5 people. The students who responded with an agreed number of 5 persons. The respondents who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people. the respondents that answered with no agreement numbered 0 individuals. The answers were very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each got a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores were summed up so that for the first statements to get a score in a row were 20, 15, 0 and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz increased the student's confidence in answering the given question. Usman et al., (2021) revealed that self-confidence is a personality aspect that expresses the strengths, abilities, and skills of the student. Self-confidence will make it easier for students to do something so that they are not hindered by low self-esteem.

Table 11. Students can dig into the relevance of computer networking and Internet material obtained from learning using Quizizz media for day-to-day as well as for school learning.

Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
7	3	0	0

Based on the results of the study, the students who answered agreed with a total of 7 people. The students who responded with an agreed number of 3 people. Student who replied with a disagreement number of 0 people. Students who reputed with a different number of people. Answers very agreed, agree, disagreed and disagree very much each get a score of 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores are summed up so that for the first statement gets a score in a row is 28, 9, 0 and 0. Based upon these scores and the references of various journals, the use of learning media Quizizz can dig into the relevance of the Computer Network and Internet material in everyday life. According to Salsabila et al., (2020) the right learning media is one of the important things to support a learning. Quizizz learning media has become one of competitive applications that are easily accessible and utilized so giving a new color to the process of evaluation by teachers.

Table 12. Total, Score and Percentage of Quizizz Implementation on the Learning Interest of Students Class XIF5 in Computer Network and Internet Materials at Senior High School 3 Surakarta

Description	Totally agree. (Skor 4)	Agree (Skor 3)	Don't agree. (Skor 2)	Very disagreeable (Skor 1)
Total	62	38	0	0
Skor	248	144	0	0
Percentage	69%	31%	0	0

Based on the results of a survey of 10 statements about Quizizz media, students who responded agreed strongly with a score of 248 and a percentage of 69%. Students who replied agreed with the score of 144 and a percent of 31%. Disagreement and strong disagreement scores are 0 and the percentages obtained are 0%. Using Quizizz as a learning medium can improve the competitiveness of students as well as motivate students in learning activities. Quizizz is an effective and efficient learning medium so that the learning process becomes more interactive and can improve student learning quality.

Conclusion

Based on the results of a survey of 10 statements about Quizizz media, students who responded agreed strongly with a score of 248 and a percentage of 69%. Students who replied agreed with the score of 144 and a percent of 31%. Disagreement and strong disagreement scores are 0 and the percentages obtained are 0%. Using Quizizz as a learning medium can improve the competitiveness of students as well as motivate students in learning activities. Quizizz is an effective and efficient learning medium so that the learning process becomes more interactive and can improve student learning quality.

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